

POLYNUCLEAR AROMATIC HYDROCARBONS. PART II. CONVENIENT SYNTHESIS OF SOME 3:4-BENZPHENANTHRENE DERIVATIVES

By V. S. GAIND, R. P. GANDHI, I. C. LAKHUMNA AND S. M. MUKHERJI

Several homologues of 3:4-benzphenanthrene, such as 2:9-dimethyl-, 2:9:3'-trimethyl- and 2:9:2':4'-tetramethyl-3:4-benzphenanthrene have been synthesised by the application of the method developed by Mukherji *et al.* (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, 19, 328). By following the same method, synthesis of 2-methyl-6-methoxy- and 2:3'-dimethyl-6-methoxy-3:4-benzphenanthrenes, as potential anti-carcinogens, has also been described.

In an earlier communication (Mukherji, Gaind and Rao, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, 19, 328) we have described an elegant and convenient synthetic route to 3:4-benzphenanthrene derivatives. This method involves cationoid reaction between a benzene derivative and a $\gamma\delta$ -unsaturated ketone, such as 2-allyl-1-tetralone system. To exploit this method further, it has now been extended to synthesis of a variety of homologues of 3:4-benzphenanthrene, following essentially the general conditions laid down by Mukherji *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

The starting material, 4-methyl-1-tetralone, was prepared from ethyl allylacetate and benzene in 74% overall yield by the procedure prescribed by Mukherji, Vig, Singh and Bhattacharyya (*ibid.*, 1953, 18, 1499). Formylation of this ketone, followed by allylation and decarbonylation, furnished 2-allyl-4-methyl-1-tetralone (IIIa) in 54% overall yield. This unsaturated ketone was then condensed with benzene, toluene and *m*-xylene in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride following exactly the condition of Mukherji, Gaind and Rao (*loc. cit.*), when the ketones (IV a, b and c) were obtained in 63%, 64% and 62% yield respectively. The orientation in the case of compounds from toluene (IVb) and *m*-xylene (IVc) was determined by their oxidative degradation with alkaline permanganate to mixtures of phthalic and terephthalic acids, and phthalic and trimelic acids respectively. No trace of *isophthalic* acid in the former case and trimellitic acid in the latter could be detected, indicating that Friedel-Crafts' alkylation under our conditions gave exclusively a single isomer. This is supported by the fact that nowhere in the products of reactions to which the compounds (IVb and IVc) were subsequently subjected, could we get any indication of the presence of other possible isomers.

[a: R₁ = H; R₂ = Me. b: R₁ = OMe; R₂ = H]

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The ketones (IVa, b and c) were reduced by the Poundorf method and the resulting carbinols (Va, b and c) cyclised with concentrated sulphuric acid at 0°. The final aromatic hydrocarbon derivatives (VIIa, b and c) were obtained by catalytic dehydrogenation of the cyclised products (VIa, b and c) over palladised charcoal (30%) (Linstead and Thomas, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 1130). These hydrocarbons were purified by regeneration from their picrates.

Our attention was then drawn to an observation by Cook and Schoental (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 288 ; 20th Annual Report of the British Empire Cancer Campaign, 1943, p. 20) that some monomethoxy derivatives of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons strongly inhibited the growth of tumours. It was therefore thought of interest to synthesise some methoxy derivatives of 3:4-benzphenanthrene with varying degree of alkylation, and to test them for physiological properties. With this end in view we have synthesised 2-methyl-6-methoxy- and 2:3'-dimethyl-6-methoxy-3:4-benzphenanthrenes following essentially the same method as described above, the starting material being 7-methoxy-1-tetralone. Formylation of 7-methoxy-1-tetralone was effected according to the conditions of Mukherji, Gaind and Rao (*loc. cit.*). It is interesting to report that in earlier attempts at C-allylation of 2-formyl-7-methoxy-1-tetralone under the conditions described for 2-formyl-1-tetralone, we found that in contrast to the simple tetralone the allylated product in the case of 7-methoxy derivative was mainly the O-derivative. C-Allylation was, however, achieved by the Claisen rearrangement of the O-allyl derivative by its thermal treatment in presence of ammonium chloride as the catalyst.

The *O*-allylated derivative is preferably represented as (A) instead of the alternative structure (B) involving enolisation of the formyl group, because on energetic grounds the former would be expected to be more stable. Furthermore, our preferential formulation (A) finds support in the generalisation postulated by Brown, Brewster and Shechter (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 467) that a reaction proceeds in such a manner as to favour the formation or retention of an *exo* double bond in the 5-membered rings and to avoid the formation or retention of the *exo* double bond in the 6-membered rings. However, this consideration would not affect the structure of the rearranged product (II b).

Hydrolysis of the *C*-allylated product furnished 2-allyl-7-methoxy-1-tetralone (III b) which was condensed with benzene and toluene in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. The orientation in the case of product (IV e) from toluene was proved, as earlier, by its oxidation with alkaline permanganate to a mixture of terephthalic and 4-methoxyphthalic acids. Terephthalic acid was identified as its dimethyl ester. No trace of isophthalic acid could be detected, indicating the *para* orientation in the Friedel-Crafts alkylation step (cf. Mukherji, Gaiind and Rao, *loc. cit.*).

The condensation products (IVd and IVe) were then reduced (Ponndorf), cyclised as above and dehydrogenated over palladium-charcoal (30%) when 2-methyl-6-methoxy- and 2,3'-dimethyl-6-methoxy-3:4-benzphenanthrenes were obtained in satisfactory overall yield. The aromatic hydrocarbon derivatives (VIIId and VIIe) were purified through regeneration from their picrates. These compounds are now under biological testing.

E X P E R I M E N T A L *

4-Methyl-1-tetralone was prepared according to the procedure of Mukherji *et al.* (*loc. cit.*, 1953).

2-Hydroxymethylene-4-methyl-1-tetralone (Ia).—Ethyl formate (9.4 g.) was added to cooled (ice-salt) suspension of dry sodium ethoxide (prepared from 3 g. sodium) in dry ether (250 c. c.) and the mixture left for 2 hours. 4-Methyl-1-tetralone (20 g.) was then added dropwise with shaking. After 6 hours the solid mass was poured onto crushed ice. The aqueous layer was separated and acidified when a red oil separated. This was taken up in ether which, after usual working up, furnished, on vacuum distillation, a light yellow oil (20 g., 80%) giving intense-red coloration

* Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Analyses are by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford.

with alcoholic ferric chloride, b. p. $145-46^{\circ}/6$ mm. (Found: C, 77.07; H, 6.00. $C_{12}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 76.59; H, 6.38 per cent).

2-Formyl-2-allyl-4-methyl-1-tetralone (II a).—The above formyl compound (20 g.) was added dropwise to an ice-cold suspension of dry sodium ethoxide (from 2.5 g. sodium) in dry benzene (200 c. c.) and left overnight. Allyl iodide (18 g.) was then added slowly and the mixture refluxed for 8 hours when the supernatant layer gave negative ferric chloride coloration test. The reaction mixture was then decomposed with iced water and extracted with benzene. Vacuum distillation of the dried extracts, after solvent removal, yielded 18 g. (75%) of (IIa) as a yellow oil, b. p. $146^{\circ}-150^{\circ}/4$ mm. (Found: C, 78.45; H, 6.72. $C_{15}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 78.94; H, 7.01 per cent).

2-Allyl-4-methyl-1-tetralone (III a).—Hydrolysis of the above oil (10 g.) was effected by stirring with 150 c. c. of 5% NaOH solution at $50^{\circ}-55^{\circ}$ for 4 hours. The hydrolysed product was acidified, extracted with ether and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent the residue on distillation under reduced pressure furnished 7.8 g. (89%) of (III a), b. p. $140-42^{\circ}/2$ mm., η_D^{25} , 1.5372. (Found: C, 83.67; H, 7.79. $C_{14}H_{16}O$ requires C, 83.96; H, 8.05 per cent).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone*, prepared in the usual manner, was crystallised from ethyl acetate-alcohol as deep orange needles, m. p. $205^{\circ}-206^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 15.20. $C_{20}H_{20}O_4N_4$ requires N, 14.73 per cent).

2-[\beta-Methyl-\beta-(phenyl)-ethyl]-4-methyl-1-tetralone (IV a).—Thiophene-free benzene (150 c. c.) was placed in a three-necked flask fitted with a mercury-sealed mechanical stirrer, a thermometer and a guard tube. Keeping the temperature at $0^{\circ}-5^{\circ}$, anhydrous aluminium chloride (14.0 g.) and 2-allyl-4-methyl-1-tetralone (10 g.) were added alternately in four lots over a period of 40 minutes. Stirring was continued for 5 hours more when a deep red colour developed. The reaction mixture was decomposed with iced HCl and extracted with benzene. The extracts, after the usual working up, yielded 8.1 g. (63%) of (IV a), b. p. $208^{\circ}-210^{\circ}/2$ mm. (Found: C, 86.06; H, 7.79. $C_{20}H_{20}O$ requires C, 86.28; H, 7.97 per cent).

2-[\beta-Methyl-\beta-(phenyl)-ethyl]-4-methyl-1-tetralol (V a).—The above ketone (6 g.) was reduced with Al-isoPrO from 2.5 g. of Al and 75 c. c. of isopropyl alcohol to obtain 5 g. (83%) of the corresponding carbinol at $196^{\circ}-200^{\circ}/2$ mm., η_D^{25} , 1.5546. (Found: C, 85.48; H, 8.56. $C_{22}H_{24}O$ requires C, 85.66; H, 8.63 per cent).

2:9-Dimethyl-1:2:9:10:11:12-hexahydro₁₃:4-benzphenanthrene (VI a).—Cyclisation of the above carbinol (4 g.) was effected with 4 c. c. of H_2SO_4 (d 1.84) at ice-bath temperature. After three hours' standing the product was diluted with water and taken up in ether. After removal of the solvent the residue on distillation under reduced pressure furnished 3.2 g. (85%) of (VIa) at $205^{\circ}-210^{\circ}/2$ mm., η_D^{25} , 1.5646. (Found: C, 91.38; H, 8.40. $C_{20}H_{22}$ requires C, 91.55; H, 8.45 per cent).

2:9-Dimethyl-3:4-benzphenanthrene (VII a).—The hexahydro compound (1.5 g.) was dehydrogenated by heating for 4 hours with 30% palladium-charcoal (0.15 g.) at $300^{\circ}-310^{\circ}$. A viscous mass was obtained on distillation under reduced pressure which readily furnished a dark red picrate. The picrate (1 g.) was decomposed with dilute ammonia to obtain the hydrocarbon (0.4 g.) which crystallised from benzene-

methanol mixture; m. p. 130° (lit. m. p. 130.6-31°; Newman and Joshel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 96). (Found: C, 93.90; H, 6.27. Calc. for C₂₀H₁₆: C, 93.71; H, 6.29 per cent).

The *picrate* of the above was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised from ethanol in dark red needles, m. p. 162° (lit. m. p. 164.6-65°; *loc. cit.*). (Found: N, 8.60. Calc. for C₂₆H₁₉O₇N₃: N, 8.65 per cent).

2-[*β*-Methyl-*β*-(*p*-tolyl)-ethyl]-4-methyl-1-tetralone (IVb).—2-Allyl-4-methyl-1-tetralone (8 g.) was allowed to react with pure toluene (75 c.c.) in presence of anhydrous AlCl₃ under the same conditions as in (III a) when 7.5 g. (64%) of (III b) was obtained, b.p. 198°-202°/2 mm., η_D^{25} , 1.5582. (Found: C, 85.83; H, 8.04. C₂₁H₂₄O requires C, 86.25; H, 8.27 per cent).

The above ketone (2 g.) was oxidised with quantitative amount of alkaline KMnO₄ solution (5%) when a mixture of phthalic and terephthalic acids was obtained. The latter, being insoluble in hot water, was separated and identified as its dimethyl ester, m. p. 140°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample of dimethyl terephthalate.

2-[*β*-Methyl-*β*-(*p*-tolyl)-ethyl]-4-methyl-1-tetralol (V b).—The above ketone (6 g.) was reduced with Al-*iso*PrO from 2.5 g. of aluminium foil in 75 c. c. of *isopropyl* alcohol. The usual working up of the product furnished 5 g. (83%) of the carbinol (V b), b. p. 206°-210°/3 mm., η_D^{25} , 1.5544. (Found: C, 85.44; H, 8.84. C₂₁H₂₆O requires C, 85.66; H, 8.90 per cent).

2:9:3'-Trimethyl-1:2:9:10:11:12-hexahydro-3:4-benzphenanthrene (VI b).—The carbinol (Vb; 4 g.) was cyclised with H₂SO₄ (conc.) as in (VI a) and after the usual working up (VI b) was obtained in 82% yield, b.p. 200°-202°/3 mm., η_D^{25} , 1.5734. (Found: C, 91.05; H, 8.67. C₂₁H₂₄ requires C, 91.30; H, 8.75 per cent).

2:9:3'-Trimethyl-3:4-benzphenanthrene (VII b).—The above hexahydro derivative (2 g.) was dehydrogenated with 30% palladium-charcoal (0.2 g.) at 300°-320° for 4 hours. The product after usual working up furnished 1.6 g. (81%) of a viscous oil which was purified by regeneration from its *picrate* and crystallised from alcohol-benzene mixture, m. p. 91°. (Found: C, 92.70; H, 6.63. C₂₁H₁₈ requires C, 91.29; H, 6.71 per cent). The *picrate*, prepared as above, was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 140°. (Found: N, 8.25. C₂₇H₂₁O₇N₃ requires N, 8.41 per cent).

2-[*β*-Methyl-*β*-(*m*-xylyl)-ethyl]-4-methyl-1-tetralone (IV c).—Pure *m*-xylene (70 c.c.) was allowed to react with 2-allyl-4-methyl-1-tetralone in presence of anhydrous AlCl₃ under the same conditions as in (IV a). The usual working up furnished 7.6 g. (62%) of (IV c), b.p. 218-22°/2 mm. (Found: C, 86.16; H, 8.28. C₂₂H₂₆O requires C, 86.23; H, 8.55 per cent).

The above ketone was oxidised with alkaline KMnO₄ when a mixture of phthalic acid and trimelic acid was obtained, the latter being identified through its trimethyl ester, m. p. 143°. (Lit. m. p. 144°; Heilbron and Bunbury, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Vol. III, p. 847).

2-[β -Methyl- β -(*m*-xylyl)-ethyl]-4-methyl-1-tetralol (Vc).—The Friedel-Crafts product (IVc; 6 g.) was subjected to reduction with aluminium isopropoxide to obtain 4.8 g. (80%) of the tetralol, b.p. 210-12°/3 mm., n_D^{20} , 1.5563. (Found: C, 85.42; H, 8.84. $C_{22}H_{22}O$ requires C, 85.66; H, 9.15 per cent).

2:9:2':4'-Tetramethyl-1:2:9:10:11:12-hexahydro-3:4-benzphenanthrene (VI c).—Cyclisation of the above tetralol (4 g.) with H_2SO_4 (conc.) at 0° for 4 hours afforded on usual working up 3.2 g. (85%) of (VI c), b.p. 193°-200°/2 mm., n_D^{20} , 1.5738. (Found: C, 90.95; H, 8.67. $C_{22}H_{26}$ requires C, 90.98; H, 9.02 per cent).

2:9:2':4'-Tetramethyl-3:4-benzphenanthrene (VII c).—The hexahydro product (2 g.) was dehydrogenated with 30% palladium-charcoal (0.2 g.) at 300°-310° for 4 hours. The product after usual working up furnished the hydrocarbon (1.8 g., 61%), b.p. 200°-205°/2 mm. Regeneration from its picrate did not furnish a solid hydrocarbon. (Found: C, 92.88; H, 6.59. $C_{22}H_{20}$ requires C, 92.97; H, 7.09 per cent).

The picrate of the above hydrocarbon was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 150°. (Found: N, 8.06. $C_{22}H_{23}O_7N_3$ requires N, 8.18 per cent).

2-Hydroxymethylene-7-methoxy-1-tetralone (I b).—7-Methoxy-1-tetralone (30 g.) was formylated, following the procedure adopted earlier, to obtain 26 g. (74%) of a light yellow mobile liquid, b.p. 170°-175°/5 mm. This gave an intense red coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 70.95; H, 5.72. $C_{13}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 70.57; H, 5.92 per cent).

The semicarbazone of the above crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 210°. (Found: N, 15.82. $C_{13}H_{15}O_3N_2$ requires N, 16.08 per cent).

2-Formyl-2-allyl-7-methoxy-1-tetralone (IIb).—The above formyl derivative (20.4 g.) was caused to react with allyl iodide under similar conditions as in (II a) to obtain 19.5 g. (80%) of *O*-allyl product. This was heated with ammonium chloride (5 g.) in an oil-bath at 180°-185° for 4 hours. After addition of water to dissolve the ammonium chloride, the oily product was extracted repeatedly with ether and the combined extracts dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removing the solvent the residue on distillation under reduced pressure furnished 19 g. of (IIb), b.p. 195°-200°/5 mm. This gave no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 73.68; H, 6.52. $C_{15}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 73.75; H, 6.60 per cent).

2-Allyl-7-methoxy-1-tetralone (IIIb).—The above product (19 g.) on hydrolysis with 5% KOH (200 c.c.) at 50°-60° furnished 13.4 g. (79%) of the tetralone (IIIb) as a pale yellow oil, b.p. 165°-170°/5 mm., n_D^{20} , 1.5532. (Found: C, 77.58; H, 7.22. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 77.77; H, 7.46 per cent).

2-[β -Methyl- β -(phenyl)-ethyl]-7-methoxy-1-tetralone (IVd).—2-Allyl-7-methoxy-1-tetralone (10.8 g.) was allowed to react with dry thiophene-free benzene in presence of anhydrous $AlCl_3$ under the conditions similar to (IVa) to obtain 9.0 g. (61%) of the tetralone (IV d), b.p. 220°-225°/4 mm., n_D^{20} , 1.5752. (Found: C, 82.02; H, 7.74. $C_{20}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 81.60; H, 7.53 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 190° (Found: N, 11.52. $C_{26}H_{26}O_6N_4$ requires N, 11.81 per cent).

2-[β -Methyl- β -(phenyl)-ethyl]-7-methoxy-1-tetralol (V d).—The above ketone (5 g.) was reduced with Al-isoPrO from 2.5 g. Al foil in 75 c.c. of isopropyl alcohol. After the usual working up, 4.2 g. (84%) of the corresponding carbinol distilled at 210°-215°/3 mm., n_D^{20} , 1.5798. (Found: C, 81.40; H, 8.40. $C_{20}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 81.04; H, 8.16 per cent).

2-Methyl-6-methoxy-1:2:9:10:11:12-hexahydro-3:4-benzphenanthrene (VI d).—Cyclisation of the above tetralol (3 g.) was effected with H_2SO_4 (conc., 3 c.c.), as described earlier. The cyclised product distilled at 210-12°/4 mm. as a gummy solid (2 g., 71%). (Found: C, 86.05; H, 7.83. $C_{20}H_{22}O$ requires C, 86.28; H, 7.97 per cent).

2-Methyl-6-methoxy-3:4-benzphenanthrene (VII d).—The above hexahydro compound (2 g.) was dehydrogenated with 30% palladium-charcoal (0.2 g.) for 4 hours at 300°-320°. On the usual working up, 1.4 g. (71%) of a viscous oil distilling at 210°-220°/4 mm. was obtained which readily furnished an orange picrate. The hydrocarbon was purified by regeneration from its picrate and crystallised from methyl alcohol in shining leaflets, m.p. 75°. (Found: C, 88.00; H, 5.86. $C_{20}H_{18}O$ requires C, 88.20; H, 5.92 per cent).

The above picrate was crystallised from ethyl alcohol, m.p. 119-20°. (Found: N, 8.31. $C_{26}H_{10}O_8N_2$ requires N, 8.38 per cent).

2-[β -Methyl- β -(p-tolyl)-ethyl]-7-methoxy-1-tetralone (IV e).—Reaction of 2-allyl-7-methyl-1-tetralone (10.5 g.) with pure toluene in the presence of anhydrous $AlCl_3$ under conditions similar to (IVa) furnished 9.5 g. (62%) of (IVe), b.p. 235°-240°/5 mm. (Found: C, 81.90; H, 7.58. $C_{21}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 81.78; H, 7.84 per cent).

The above ketone (2 g.) was oxidised with alkaline $KMnO_4$ as earlier, when a mixture of terephthalic acid and 4-methoxyphthalic acid was obtained. The former was separated due to its greater insolubility in hot water and identified as its methyl ester, m.p. 142°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample of dimethyl terephthalate. 4-Methoxyphthalic acid melted at 162° (lit. m.p. 164°; Fritsch, *Annalen*, 1897, 296, 357).

2-[β -Methyl- β -(p-tolyl)-ethyl]-7-methoxy-1-tetralol (Ve).—The Ponndorf reduction of the above ketone (6 g.) was effected as in the earlier cases and the corresponding tetralol distilling at 230°-235°/5 mm. was obtained (4.8 g., 80%). (Found: C, 80.90; H, 8.20. $C_{21}H_{26}O_2$ requires C, 81.25; H, 8.44 per cent).

2:3'-Dimethyl-6-methoxy-1:2:9:10:11:12-hexahydro-3:4-benzphenanthrene (VIe).—The above carbinol (3 g.) was cyclised with 3 c.c. of sulphuric acid (conc.) in the usual manner to obtain 2 g. (72%) of the hexahydro compound, distilling at 225°-230°/5 mm. (Found: C, 85.81; H, 8.22. $C_{21}H_{24}O$ requires C, 86.25; H, 8.27 per cent).

2:3'-Dimethyl-6-methoxy-3:4-benzphenanthrene (VII e).—Dehydrogenation of the hexahydro compound (1 g.) with 30% palladium-charcoal gave, on usual working up, a viscous oil (0.7 g., 60%) distilling at 230° - $235^{\circ}/5$ m m. This was converted into its picrate and the hydrocarbon regenerated therefrom was crystallised from methyl alcohol in shining plates, m.p. 79° . (Found: C, 87.80; H, 6.22. $C_{21}H_{18}O$ requires C, 88.08; H, 6.34 per cent).

Picrate of the above was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 124° . (Found: N, 7.95. $C_{27}H_{21}O_8N_3$ requires N, 8.15 per cent).

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
PUNJAB UNIVERSITY,
HOSHARPUR.

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